

AI AND PERFORMERS' RIGHTS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

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ELENA COOPER

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Dr Elena Cooper**

Abstract

This article uses legal history as a vantage point for reflecting on the current moment in the debate about AI and performers' rights. Current debates often refer to 'creators' and/or 'copyright' as generic categories denoting both performers and authors. Legal history, I argue, sharpens the critical lens on current debate by drawing our attention to what today remains different about the legal rules protecting performers. That difference, at present, leaves performers less well placed to deal with the challenge of AI than authors and also goes to the heart of Equity's current reform proposals. That difference should now be debated.

Last year, I published an Opinion in the *E.I.P.R. - Copyright History as a Critical Lens* – a follow-up to *Interrogating Copyright History* (an *E.I.P.R.* Opinion that I co-authored with Ronan Deazley in 2016).¹ I argued that the study of law in past times can be a powerful critical lens on how we see the legal present. Whether the past reveals a story of continuity or change, there is, I argued:

value in looking backwards, before we look forwards: an historical perspective helps us to recover the contingency of the present, to imagine things differently and to look to the future with a more critical eye.²

My comments should be read in the light of a wider 'historical turn' in critical thinking about intellectual property law in the last two decades, following the publication in 1999 of *The Making of Modern Intellectual Property Law* by Brad Sherman and Lionel Bently. Sherman and Bently's historical work showed that the categories of intellectual property that we know today, are not timeless, natural or inevitable; 'theory... played at best an *ex post facto* role' in later legitimating the legal categories that emerged. In so doing, Sherman and Bently opened the way for legal

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¹ E. Cooper, 'Copyright History as a Critical Lens', (2022) 43(3) EIPR 128–131. E. Cooper and R. Deazley, 'Interrogating Copyright History', (2016) 38(8) EIPR 467–470.

² E. Cooper, 'Copyright History as a Critical Lens', (2022) 43(3) EIPR 128–131, 131.

historians to probe critical questions about the legal present and future of intellectual property law.³

In this article, I provide an example of looking backwards before we look forwards. I demonstrate the critical value of an historical long-lens on a discrete strand of current legal debates raised by cutting-edge technology today: a facet of the impact of Artificial Intelligence technology (or 'AI') on performers, particularly actors, and the search today for an appropriate legal response. Equity, the UK actors' trade union launched a campaign last year, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, seeking the legislative reform of statutory performers' rights, specifically the increase in the scope of legal protection.⁴ However, the UK Government has, so far, resisted reform. The UK Government's position on performers' rights is indicated in the closing paragraphs of its response to the UK Intellectual Property Office's consultation *AI and IP: Copyright and Patents*. Referring to proposals for 'an expansion of the scope of performers' rights in the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988', the UK Government comments as follows:

at this stage, the impacts of AI technologies on performers remain unclear. It is also unclear whether and how existing law (both in the IP framework and beyond it) is insufficient to address any issues. If intervention is necessary, the IP system may not be the best vehicle for this. We will keep these issues under review from an IP perspective.⁵

How might an historical perspective enable us critically to reflect on the present moment in the debate of the future of performers' rights?

Technology in the 21st century: Aspects of the challenge of AI today

Before I look to the past, I start with today. AI is technology that uses machine-based learning to perform functions that were previously the province of usually slower, more costly and/or more labour-intensive processes undertaken by human beings. AI has a wide field of application from medical diagnosis, robotics, to the management of insurance-risk.⁶ However, one set of

³ B. Sherman and L. Bently, *The Making of Modern Intellectual Property Law: The British Experience, 1760-1911*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1999), p.206 and p.p.215-220. On the 'historical turn' in intellectual property scholarship see also Cooper and Deazley, 'Interrogating Copyright History', (2016) 38(8) EIPR 467-470, 467 and M. Kretschmer with L. Bently and R. Deazley, 'Introduction: The History of Copyright History: Notes from an Emerging Discipline' in R. Deazley, M. Kretschmer and L. Bently (eds), *Privilege and Property: Essays on the History of Copyright* (Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2010), p.p.2-3.

⁴ Equity, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, April 2022, available at www.equity.org.uk/campaigns.

⁵ UK Intellectual Property Office, *Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property: copyright and patents: Government response to consultation*, 28 June 2022, available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations>, 'Other issues raised by respondents', para. 83.

⁶ Schumpeter, 'A Battle Royal is Brewing over Copyright and AI', *The Economist*, 15 March 2023: AI has 'implications that extend beyond the creative industries to any business where machine-learning plays a role'.

questions for intellectual property law today relates to AI's impact on authors and performers working in a variety of sectors.

The creative potential of AI technology has been embraced by some visual artists and AI has been hailed elsewhere as democratising creativity, by providing everyone with the tools to create cultural works.⁷ AI technology also offers new possibilities for enhancing human performances, for instance, in the creation of video games, in turn opening opportunities for actors.⁸ Yet, there are also reports that AI is, in certain contexts, increasingly *replacing* human authors and performers, and putting them out of work. A good example of this is the audio performance sector, where AI generated voices can now be used to undertake audio work (e.g. audio books) or provide voice-overs at negligible cost, in circumstances where a professional actor would previously have been employed. Redundancy for actors caused by the introduction of AI – the replacement of humans by machines – is reported to be now increasingly commonplace.⁹

While AI can replace human authors and performers, it also frequently utilises their pre-existing work. AI learns by tracking patterns in an existing body of material: a 'data-set'. In the case of visual images produced by AI, the data-set may comprise large quantities of copyright-protected visual images scraped from the internet without copyright clearance.¹⁰ For AI produced voices, the data-set may be a collection of recordings of human voices, which may have been recorded by actors for another unrelated purpose (e.g. a casting or audition) and included in the data-set without consent. Alternatively, the data-set may comprise recordings that were licensed to a third party for broad purposes, e.g. 'for research', yet particularly where the licence pre-dates AI technology, AI uses were not specifically contemplated by the parties at the time the contract was concluded.¹¹

In addition to the AI learning process, the material generated by AI – for instance images generated in response to a text prompt – may involve 'copying' through a new means: computer

⁷ These perspectives were explored recently in presentations by Prof. James Stewart and Prof. Sarah Cook at the event Generative AI in the Cultural World, CREATE, University of Glasgow, held on 14 March 2023.

⁸ Evidence of Paul Fleming, General Secretary of Equity, to the House of Commons Science, Innovation and Technology Committee, 10 May 2023, 'Oral evidence: Governance of Artificial Intelligence (AI)', HC 945, at Q.327, which post-dates the acceptance of this article by the E.I.P.R..

⁹ See for example, O. Horstein, 'Stop AI Stealing the Show: Why Artists Fear Rise of Synthetic Performances', UK Tech News: <https://www.uktech.news/>, 27 June 2022: 'AI systems are increasingly taking jobs from skilled professional performers due to AI seeming like a cheaper and more convenient option.'

¹⁰ Schumpeter, 'A Battle Royal is Brewing over Copyright and AI', The Economist, 15 March 2023.

¹¹ On such issues and how AI uses relate to existing contracts see J. Body, 'AI Stealing Voice-Over Jobs, Experts Warn', The Stage, 27 March 2023, as well as the quotations from Equity members in Stop AI Stealing the Show, April 2022, 'Survey Findings' p.p.4-7.

synthetisation.¹² In relation to performance, prior to AI technology, the circumstances in which a performance could be copied, without direct taking from a recording itself, were more limited and confined to human imitation such as a sound-a-like imitating an actor's voice, as in the passing off case of *Sim v Heinz* (discussed further below).¹³ By contrast, AI technology today opens a future in which a performance, or aspects of a performance, can be recreated through technology, without direct copying from the recording. Equity, adopting the arguments of Mathilde Pavis in *Artificial Intelligence and Performers' Rights*, refers to these new modes of copying performances, via 'digital sound and look-alike', as 'performance synthetisation'.¹⁴

Whether or not performers are sufficiently protected is, of course, tied to the distinct circumstances raised by the new and unprecedented technologies of today: the challenge for legislators and the courts is to strike the right balance of interests in a specific technological context and then (as in the case of the *Economics of Music Streaming Enquiry* in recent times¹⁵) to continue to track how well that 'balance' operates in practice. How, then, can the past help us to reflect on debates about AI and performers today?

Looking backwards: new technology and the law in past times

The history of copyright law - which dates back to printing privileges introduced with the advent of the printing press - is itself inextricably intertwined with the story of technological change. Copyright protection through Act of Parliament dates back to the early eighteenth century - the Statute of Anne 1710 (which protected books) - but it was in the mid to late nineteenth century that copyright, and the intellectual property system more generally, emerged in a modern form.¹⁶ In the nineteenth century, one cutting-edge new technology was photography, which by the 1850s had become a relatively cheap and easy medium of mass reproduction. While books, as

¹² Complaint, *Getty Images v Stability AI*, filed 3 February 2023, United States District Court for the District of Delaware, p.3, para. 7: 'Stability AI has created an image-generating model called Stable Diffusion that uses artificial intelligence to deliver computer-synthesized images in response to text prompts.' Proceedings involving the same parties have also been issued in England and Wales, in the High Court, London: A. Williams, 'Does AI Image Generation infringe Copyright? Getty Thinks So' *Evening Standard*, 19 January 2023: 'Getty Images claims Stability AI 'infringed intellectual property rights including copyright' by using its database of images to train the AI'.

¹³ See text to n.65-70 below.

¹⁴ Equity, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, April 2022, p.11, quoting Mathilde Pavis, 'Artificial intelligence and Performers' Rights', Submission to the UK Intellectual Property Office, 30 November 2020, responding to the Response to the UK Intellectual Property Office, Call for Views on Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property, 2020. See also M. Pavis, 'Rebalancing our Regulatory Response to Deepfakes with Performers' Rights', *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 2021, 974-998, 991, recommending, amongst other things, protection for the 'reproduction of performances via synthetisation.'

¹⁵ Digital, Culture, Media and Sport Select Committee, *Second Report of Session 2021-22, Economics of Music Streaming (HC 50)*, 9 July 2021.

¹⁶ See Sherman and Bently, *The Making of Modern Intellectual Property*, p.3.

well as engravings and sculptures were all protected by copyright Acts passed during the course of the eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, paintings were *not* protected until the passage of the Fine Arts Copyright Act 1862, which was passed in response to technological change as well as other factors.¹⁷

A pressing concern for painters in the 1850s, was the disruption caused by unauthorised photography, to the highly lucrative reproduction market for prints of paintings, that had made painters richer than they had ever been before.¹⁸ In the court room, in copyright infringement cases brought against photographers in the 1850s (relying on engraving copyright) it was claimed that if painters and their intermediaries (the printsellers) were powerless to stop unauthorised photographs, 'pictures would not be painted'.¹⁹ Also at stake was the livelihood of a class of reproductive engravers, highly skilled in translating a painting though 'a wonderful combination of lines and touches'; in the view of the engraver Charles Landseer, photography was '*foe-tographic art*'.²⁰

Yet, new photographic technology in the nineteenth century – like AI technology today – was also amazing. Even nineteenth century judges, in judgments ruling that unauthorised photographs were infringing, also marvelled at the quality of the infringements: in *Gambart v Ball* (1863) Willes J. described the defendant's photographs as 'wonderfully good' and Keating J. noted the 'beautiful array of photographic copies' in the streets, that 'meets the eye at every turn'.²¹ The argument posed in the press, then, was whether copyright *should* regulate new technology in this way; as magistrates began to crack down against photographic infringers under new summary powers protecting painting copyright under the Fine Arts Copyright Act 1862, *The Daily News* asked whether copyright infringement was the appropriate legal response. Two of the most notorious photographic infringers of prints of paintings were Samuel Benoni Beal and Henry Ashford, based in the City of London, who founded The Photographic Protection Society to raise a defence fund to fight infringement cases. On one view, said *The Daily News*, Beal and Ashford were 'enterprising tradesmen' to whom the public was indebted for the provision of 'so good an article at so moderate a price'. No one would complain that 'the railways have driven the

¹⁷ See E. Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright: The Contested Image*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), Chapter 1, p.p.1-2, p.p.18-19 and Chapter 2.

¹⁸ Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.22, p.p.115-116 and p.p.221-222. L. Bently, 'Art and the Making of Modern Copyright Law', in D. McClean and K. Schubert (eds), *Dear Images: Art Copyright and Culture* (London: Ridinghouse RCA, 2002), p.p.331-351.

¹⁹ Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.225, quoting submissions of Counsel for the printseller Henry Graves in *Graves v Augustus Mound* (1867).

²⁰ Bently, 'Art and the Making of Modern Copyright Law', p.340, quoting W. Frith, *My Autobiography* (London, Richard Bentley & Son, 1887), p.212.

²¹ 'Gambart v. Ball', *The Times*, 13 December, 1862, p.11, *Gambart v. Ball* (1863) 14 C.B. (N.S.) 306, 315; 143 ER 463, 467, discussed in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.229.

coaches off the public roads, and shut up many a wayside inn', so why, asked *The Daily News* in 1868, should copyright law hold back a technological 'revolution in art'?²²

The implicit answer to this question in the mid nineteenth century, from both the legislature and the courts, lay with the societal value attributed to painting. Unlike the wayside inns on the old coach-ways, redundant with the arrival of the new railway network, painters required legal protection. One objective underpinning the new legislation in 1862 was, therefore, to protect painters 'who contributed by their art to the honour of this country, the elevation of public taste, and to the amusement, instruction and delight of the people'.²³ Further, the courts' interpretation of existing legal rights (under the Engraving Acts) sought 'to encourage the arts' through 'securing to the artist' the 'money value of the creation of the artists' mind'.²⁴

This historical example highlights the, to date, *opposite* legislative response today, to performers' demands for new protection in the face of technological change. Of course, legal history is *not* an evolutionary process; that new rights were granted in the mid nineteenth century, does not mean that the legislature should act in a similar way today.²⁵ How, then, can an historical perspective help us to reflect on the present moment in the debate of performers' rights?

An historical lens on AI debates today

One of the jumping-off points for this article, is my observation of a recent panel discussion held online, in March 2023, forming part of the *AI/ML Media Advocacy Summit*. The Summit, through regular on-line events (of which this was the first) aims both 'to help protect artist rights in the fast-growing AI and technology space' as well as 'to educate our community as well as the public' regarding unethical technological practice.²⁶ While the Summit included panels from all parts of the globe, the focus here is on the UK panel discussion, which comprised Derek Brazell (Association of Illustrators), Isabelle Doran (Association of Photographers), Laurence Bouvard (Equity) and the solicitor Gabrielle Playford (from the media and entertainment specialist law firm Sheridans), with Darrell Warner (an independent artist and illustrator) as moderator.

The UK panel discussion comprised high-quality debate about the challenge of AI, the current state of copyright law, and what the future might hold, and a recording of the full discussion is

²² 'A Case Before Robert Carden at Guildhall', *The Daily News*, 27 February 1868, p.4, discussed in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p. 225.

²³ Parl. Deb., vol.166 ser. 3, col. 2018, 22 May 1862, Lord Westbury, Attorney General.

²⁴ *Gambart v. Ball* (1863) 14 C.B. (N.S.) 306, 315; 143 E.R. 463, 468, per Erle CJ discussed in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.p.228-242.

²⁵ On this point, see Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.251.

²⁶ <https://www.aimlmediaadvocacy.com>.

available to watch online²⁷ and is recommended to readers of the *E.I.P.R.*. Here I focus on one discrete aspect of the debate: the inclusion, on the panel, of an actress (Bouvard), alongside two representatives of visual artists: illustrators (Brazell) and photographers (Doran).

What was clear, in the terms of the UK panel discussion, was the social and creative parity accorded today to visual artists (illustrators and photographers) and actors. The language used by the panellists often referred to both actors and visual artists together as ‘creators’ or ‘creatives’, and that fed into one of the panel’s conclusions: while the challenges for different sectors might in some ways be distinct, there was also the need for a ‘collective response’ to AI, bringing together all ‘content creators’. From a societal perspective, then, implicit in the terms of the discussion, were that we accord equal creative value to actors *and* visual artists.

At a first glance, this might seem an unremarkable observation. However, the panel’s focus on the *social* parity of actors and visual artists today, masked their different *legal* treatment: actors as performers protected by performers’ rights, and visual artists as authors protected by copyright. That difference in legal treatment is particularly stark if we look to legal history: the legal protection of performers historically has always been lesser to that accorded to ‘authors’ of authorial works²⁸ by copyright.²⁹ While today, we are fast-approaching parity of legal rights between authors and performers,³⁰ performers’ rights and copyright rules (while often mirroring each other³¹) are nevertheless distinct areas of legal regulation.³² Further, and crucially, AI technology is one area which *exposes* one of the key differences between performers’ rights and copyright that persists today: scope of protection. Performers’ rights today are narrow in scope and confined to copying from the *recording*; copying the *performance* itself, is not an infringement of statutory performers’ rights (though, as I explain later, it may be passing off).³³

²⁷ <https://www.aimlmediaadvocacy.com>.

²⁸ The use of the term ‘authorial copyright’ is intended to indicate that the analysis in this section does not apply to entrepreneurial works such as sound recordings, broadcasts, cable programmes, typographical arrangements.

²⁹ On the history of legal protection for performances see R. Arnold, *Performers’ Rights* (6th Ed., London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2021), Chapter 1.

³⁰ L. Bently and B. Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law*, 6th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), p.371: ‘In all but two respects... namely duration and depth of protection’, protection for performers in the UK is now at a ‘level virtually equivalent to that of authors.’

³¹ For example, under s. 189 and Schedule 2 Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988, exceptions to rights in performances ‘correspond broadly’ to exceptions to copyright infringement.

³² ‘Rights in Performances’ are contained in Chapter II of the Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988, and therefore separate from the rules of ‘Copyright’ contained in Chapter I of the same Act.

³³ See, for example, the definition of performers’ property rights contained in s.182A (reproduction), s.182B (distribution), s.182C (rental and lending) and s.182CA (making available), Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988. Passing off is discussed below, text to n.60–62. See also the discussion in R. Arnold, ‘Performers’ Rights and Artificial Intelligence’ in R. Abbott (ed), *Research Handbook on intellectual property and Artificial Intelligence*, (Cheltenham and Northampton: Edward Elgar) p.p.218–224, p.221.

By contrast copyright provides authors of authorial works (including visual artists like photographers and illustrators) with a far deeper scope of protection.³⁴ Therefore, an important point absent from the recent Summit's UK panel discussion, was the *difference* in legal protection for performers and authors: not all 'creators' represented on the panel are today equally equipped against AI uses in terms of legal rights, even though they are affected in similar ways.³⁵ I argue that a long-term historical perspective on the present – comparing the very different approach to scope of protection for authors and performers – sharpens the critical lens on current debates raised by AI today.

Comparing Performers and Authors

What is the history of protection for copyright 'authors' (i.e. not performers)? As Isabella Alexander shows in *Copyright and the Public Interest*, the history of copyright is a story of expansion in protection. In the eighteenth century, copyright was merely a limited right to print and reprint a particular text: it was '*copy-right*'. By the early twentieth century, a far broader idea of infringement had taken hold.³⁶ There were a number of facets in this expansion in protection, and I look at two here: first, expansion in exclusive rights, and secondly, protection for the abstract work.

Comparing authors and performers: exclusive rights

Part of growth in protection for authors charted by Alexander is in the range of exclusive rights granted by copyright – the expansion in the range of the acts which the copyright owner can control – and that expansion has continued into the twenty-first century through the introduction of new exclusive rights by legislation. Statutory copyright began in the eighteenth century only as a right to control printing and re-printing, but as a result of piecemeal historical expansion, under current legislation, the copyright owner can now control a broad range of uses, including the following acts of primary infringement: reproduction, issuing to the public, rental or lending, performance in public, communication to the public, adaptation.³⁷ Importantly, these

³⁴ Copyright restricts acts (e.g. reproduction, issue to the public, rental and lending, making available) in relation to the work: s.16(1) Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988. The deeper scope of protection for copyright works is explained below, text to n.44-47.

³⁵ AI, of course, also raises specific issues for performers, which may not affect visual artists. For a comprehensive discussion see: M. Pavis, 'Rebalancing our Regulatory Response to Deepfakes with Performers' Rights', *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 2021, 974-998

³⁶ I. Alexander, *Copyright and the Public Interest in the Nineteenth Century*, (Oxford and Portland, Oregon: Hart Publishing) Chapter 6, p.155.

³⁷ S.16(1) Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988.

exclusive rights are (and have always been³⁸) *property* rights: whereas they are granted (with some exceptions) to the author at first instance, they are fully transferrable to a third party (e.g. by licence or assignment).³⁹

How does the protection of performers compare? As regards exclusive rights, the history of protection of performers was far slower. There was no statutory protection for performances until 1925, and that legislation merely granted limited rights for anyone to bring criminal proceedings against the unauthorised recording of a live performance; it did *not* provide exclusive rights in the nature of property, and that difference between authors and performers was enshrined at an international level in the Rome Convention 1961.⁴⁰ Legislative reform in 1988 granted performers and those with whom they enter into exclusive recording contracts, for the first time, civil rights, but these 'non-property rights' (which remain in force today) are expressly separate from and lesser to the copyright protection granted to authors.⁴¹ The shift towards granting performers economic rights that more closely resemble the more comprehensive copyright protection for authors came in the 1990s: the UK implementation of the EU Rental and Lending Rights Directive by the UK Copyright and Related Rights Regulations 1996.⁴² As a consequence, performers' rights today include 'performers' property rights' - the right of reproduction, issuing to the public, rental right and lending right, and the making available right - which are fully transferrable to third parties.⁴³

³⁸ The ability to transfer copyright to a third party is a key feature of all copyright statutes going back to the eighteenth century, starting with the Statute of Anne 1710. The full text of historic statutes can be found in the online resource Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900), eds. L. Bently and M. Kretschmer, www.copyrighthistory.org.

³⁹ Section 11 and Section 90, Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988.

⁴⁰ The Dramatic and Musical Performers Protection Act 1925. Unlike the Berne Convention on Copyright that has always, since 1886, mandated the provision of exclusive rights for authors in relation to their work, the Rome Convention 1961 (Art. 7(1)) merely obliges contracting states to provide performers with 'the possibility of preventing' narrower uses of performances (even though it grants by Art.10 and 13, exclusive rights to 'authorise or prohibit' to owners of copyright in sound recordings and broadcasts); specifically, it was contemplated, by drafters of the Rome Convention, that the phrase 'the possibility of preventing' did not require the grant of property rights in performances. See further, Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.p.19-22, 1-53 to 1-58.

⁴¹ Sections 192A, 192B, 193 and 194 Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988.

⁴² Council Directive 92/100/EEC, 19 November 1992, and UK SI 1996/2967, reg. 21(1).

⁴³ Section 191A(1), Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988, referring to sections 182A, 182B, 182C and 182CA Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988. On transmission to third parties, see section 191B, Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988. The term of protection for performers' property rights, however, is different to the term of exclusive rights granted by authorial copyright. The duration of authorial copyright is the life of the author plus 70 years (section 12(2) Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988), whereas performers' rights last for a period of 50 years from the end of the year that the performance took place, but this period can be extended by an additional 50 years where a recording is released or 70 years where a sound recording is released (section 191(2) Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988). See also Bently and Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law*, p.377.

The introduction of ‘performers’ property rights’ in 1996, then, is one basis on which commentators correctly identify a close parity today between the protection of authors and performers. It is one way in which it *is* meaningful to refer to performers’ rights as ‘copyright’ in a loose lay-person sense, as was the case in the recent UK panel discussion. However, parity between authors and performers is *not* the full picture and, as I argue in the next section, AI brings this persisting difference to the fore.

Comparing authors and performers: the abstract work vs. the recording

Returning to Alexander’s historical account, another facet in the expansion in infringement of authorial copyright,⁴⁴ primarily the province of judicial case-law is the notion that copyright protects ‘an *abstract*’work’.⁴⁵ For example, case law decided in twentieth century established that copyright in literary and dramatic works would be infringed not only by a verbatim taking from the words on the page – literal copying – but also taking what Bently and Sherman today term ‘the non-literal elements of a novel or play’ such as the plot, the storyline or incidents and themes.⁴⁶ In artistic copyright, a nineteenth century example of non-literal copying, can be seen in *Brooks v Religious Tract Society* (1897) which concerned an illustration for a children’s story produced by the defendant: the defendant’s taking of the ‘form and attitude’ of one of the figures (the dog), along with the background and foreground, of the plaintiff’s work amounted to infringement, because the defendant had reproduced the ‘feeling and artistic character’ of the plaintiff’s work.⁴⁷

What about the history of the scope of protection for performers? Do performers also receive protection for their *performance* as an abstract creative work? The answer is ‘no’. As will be apparent from the last section, at the point that *Brooks* was decided, as well as a number of cases establishing the abstract scope of literary and dramatic copyright,⁴⁸ performers had no legal protection for their performances at all. Further, all the statutory reforms that followed, confined legal protection to copying from the *recording* alone and that is the legal position today: there is, and there never has been, any statutory protection for a performer’s original

⁴⁴ The analysis in this section does not apply to entrepreneurial works such as sound recordings, broadcasts, cable programmes, typographical arrangements, due to the manner in which these works are defined in Chapter 1, Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988.

⁴⁵ Alexander, *Copyright Law and the Public Interest in the Nineteenth Century*, p.p.155–156. Emphasis added.

⁴⁶ Bently and Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law*, 6th ed., p.p.231–232.

⁴⁷ *Brooks v. Religious Tract Society* [1897] 45 WR 476 discussed in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.217.

⁴⁸ Bently and Sherman cite, for example, *Rees v Melville* [1914] MacG C 168: see Bently and Sherman *Intellectual Property Law*, 6th ed., p.231 n.128.

performance as an abstract creative work. This is one of the key differences between authorial copyright⁴⁹ and performers' rights that remains today.

Scope of Protection and AI: Why it matters today

At the present moment there is, to borrow Sherman and Bently's phrase, a 'need to remember' the history of legal protection for performers.⁵⁰ Just because it is now meaningful to talk about performers as if they are copyright authors in terms of, for example, exclusive rights, does not mean that we should overlook the continuing legal differences between performers and authors, which stem from their different treatment historically.

Indeed, it is this point of difference in the current legal treatment of performers (as compared to authors), that goes to the heart of one of the key proposals in Equity's *Stop AI Stealing the Show*: Equity's campaign to reform statutory performers' rights 'to protect performers against AI-made performance synthetisation' is, of course, a demand for a legislative response to new technology.⁵¹ However, on one view, express protection against synthetisation is required *because* of the narrow legal protection for performances (as compared to authorial works) in the current legal framework. While we lack an in-depth monograph-length study on the history of the protection of performers,⁵² it is clear that at least some of the reasons that historically separated performers from authors would be subject to challenge today. For example, the narrow scope of performers' rights stems from their classification as 'related rights' outside copyright and Richard Arnold, writing extra-judicially, attributes that classification to the view that performers were 'less deserving of protection since their contribution is subsidiary to that of authors'.⁵³ This assumption sits uneasily with social reality today, as reflected in the terms of the recent *AI/ML Media Advocacy Summit*; today, as Arnold states, writing extra-judicially, "as far as the moral case is concerned, a performance is as much of an intellectual and aesthetic creation as a copyright work".⁵⁴

Accordingly, the current narrow scope of performers' rights may *also* be unsustainable on principles that *pre-date* the advent of AI. A broader scope for performers' rights is, in the view of the current author, the logical consequence of what Richard Arnold, writing extra-judicially in the pre-AI environment, has advocated as the 'first task' to reform performers' rights: 'to bring

⁴⁹ On my use of the phrase 'authorial copyright', see n.44 above.

⁵⁰ Sherman and Bently, *The Making of Modern Intellectual Property Law*, p. 219.

⁵¹ Equity, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, April 2022, under 'Recommendations to Government' p.8.

⁵² In the absence of a monograph-length study of the history of the protection of performers, the reader is referred to the account in Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, Chapter 1.

⁵³ Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.8, 1-18, (1).

⁵⁴ Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.7, 1-18.

performers into the copyright fold proper, rather than to continue to pretend that performers' rights are in some way different to other copyrights'.⁵⁵ Legal history, then, exposes the contingency of the current treatment of performers by intellectual property law today. The current legal status of performers is neither inevitable nor the reflection of any universal truth. In exposing the contingency of the current legal framework, history allows us to imagine things differently.

So, what if history *had* been different, and protection for performers had extended to performance as an abstract creative work? First, we would today have 100 years of case law establishing a sophisticated understanding of the meaning of 'original performance', both what is protected and what is not, in the same way as we today have nuanced judicial guidance as to how protection of a literary work extends to plot, themes and incidents. Secondly, with a broader scope of rights, Equity members would now be before the courts, establishing the parameters of their existing rights in new technological circumstances (as a copyright holder is doing in the case of artistic copyright works in *Getty v Stability AF*⁵⁶), rather than waiting for legislative action to bring new rights into existence; the process of adapting existing concepts to AI would *not* necessarily require parliamentary action and yet more convoluted piecemeal amendments to an already highly complex statutory framework.

Accordingly, looking backwards before looking forwards, I argue, means we should not be confined by existing intellectual property categories. Parliament should consider seriously the merits of the proposal made by Richard Arnold, writing extra-judicially, for the wholesale assimilation, in terms of the nature of legal protection, of performers to authors. Of course, not all technological changes can be anticipated by legislation, and there will be other ways in which the protection of performers in an AI-world raises distinct issues.⁵⁷ However, by granting performers broader statutory rights that more meaningfully reflect their creative status today, the legislature will be enabling the courts, in a wider range of circumstances, to continue to adapt those rights to other new technologies of the future. Drafting rules that provide the courts with interpretative freedom, is how best to introduce flexibility in intellectual property legislation. Further, performers' rights are subject to defences to infringement and these currently include exceptions for caricature, parody, pastiche and quotation. Accordingly, already

⁵⁵ Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.51, 1-116. On the significance of Richard Arnold's treatise *Performers' Rights*, both historically and in relation to current debates, see the forthcoming review by the current author in (2023) 34 *Entertainment Law Review* 104-105.

⁵⁶ See n.12 above.

⁵⁷ On this, see M. Pavis, 'Rebalancing our Regulatory Response to Deepfakes with Performers' Rights', *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 2021, 974-998.

embedded in the structure of performers' rights is a means to ensure balance in how that wider scope of protection is applied.⁵⁸

Technology and its Cultural Consequences in the Past and Today

A long historical lens also reminds us that technology has cultural consequences. Famously, the theorist Walter Benjamin in his seminal essay *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*, wrote about the loss of aura to the original work of art in an age of mass reproduction.⁵⁹ One of the great strengths of the recent *AI/ML Media Advocacy Summit* UK Panel discussion, was that the panellists also contemplated the cultural consequences of technology. AI, explained Bouvard (an actress, who also has a computer science background) is 'about finding the pattern that already exists and making a new version of it'; it is, by definition, not about 'diversity and difference'. By contrast, what 'makes art so exciting', argued Bouvard, is precisely 'going for the outlier, and the different view and the twist on things'. Viewing Bouvard's comments in the light of Benjamin's essay, AI too is likely to have deep-rooted *cultural* consequences.

It is important that lawyers think about these cultural consequences of technological change: the legal choices we make today, can and will impact on this future cultural landscape. In Bouvard's comments, then, is a *justification* for legal protection: our intellectual property system should support diversity and difference in the creative arts and providing human performers with adequate legal rights, that reflect creativity in performance, is a crucial first step. In doing so, we will be providing the legal conditions for performers to retain their livelihoods by *adapting* to new AI technology, both through the possibility of establishing new income streams and through the control of the integrity of their work.

Further, considering the cultural consequences of new AI technology provides a basis for revisiting the weaknesses of certain existing legal rules. For example, in the UK, actors have moral rights as regards audio performances, but these (like moral rights for authors) must be asserted and can be waived through contract.⁶⁰ The UK Panel discussion indicated that, in the field of audio work (e.g. audio-books) for the majority of actors - to borrow Bouvard's terms, ordinary 'jobbing actors' (who undertake discrete pieces of creative work for different parties) but are not 'stars' or well-known 'names' - attribution rights mean very little in practice: such actors are generally *not* credited in audio work, even for a leading role, and their anonymity

⁵⁸ Schedule 2, Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988, para. 2A and para. 2(1ZA).

⁵⁹ W. Benjamin, *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*, 1935, in W. Benjamin, *Illuminations*, (New York: Schocken Books, 1968).

⁶⁰ Section 205D and 205J(2) Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988.

heightens the industry perception that actors *can* be replaced by machines.⁶¹ As Bouvard explained, in relation to audio-books: 'In our industry... there is a that sense of 'we don't know who you are, so we won't put you in the credits', but if you aren't in the credits, then anyone can do the job, so let's get a robot to do it.' As we look forward to how best to support human performers in an AI saturated world, we should consider whether more *robust* legal rights of attribution – not requiring assertion and subject to waiver in only narrow circumstances – are justified, both to maintain authenticity in creative work (by distinguishing the work of humans from machines) and to allow actors to be identified and therefore potentially hired for other creative work.

Again, I turn to an historical example, as a means of highlighting the potential for attribution to be an author's or performer's counterweight at a time of changing cultural power relations: the links between early forerunners to moral rights (section 7 of the Fine Arts Copyright Act 1862, which applied also to photographs) and the unionisation of photographers in the 1890s. In the late nineteenth century, as photography was increasingly organised on an industrial model with photographers employed by large commercial firms organised as factories, the Photographic Workers' Union considered its campaign for attribution on each photograph of the photographer employee that had taken the photograph (rather than only the name of the photographic firm), to be as important as the Union's campaign for clean air, basic safety at work, and a shorter working day. Why? Attribution ensured that photographer employees were known for their work and could then be hired elsewhere.⁶² While the context of the Victorian factory might seem far removed from the working-life of an ordinary 'jobbing actor' today, the example clearly shows the importance of attribution to author/performer empowerment: attribution can be a counterbalance in favour of authors or performers to structural changes that might otherwise render them invisible, whether industrial 'authorship' (claimed by employers) in the nineteenth century, or AI technology in the twenty-first century.

Performers and the Common Law

So far, the main focus of this article has been on legislation and its reform by parliament. However, history shows that also important in this area is the common law, developed through

⁶¹ The legal basis for the lack of credit – whether waiver, lack of assertion or non-enforcement – was not given in the discussion, but elsewhere Bouvard commented more generally on contractual practice as follows: 'we are bought out and often in the contracts we have it says 'you sign over your rights, in perpetuity, in the known universe, for any technology now in the future' and if you don't, you don't get paid and you are not used.'

⁶² J.A. Randall, *The Photographic Worker: Trade Unionism and Co-operation Applied to Photography* (London: J.A. Randall, 1896) and the discussion in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.66.

judicial decisions.⁶³ For example, original historical work into actors, reveals the importance of the courts in safeguarding the position of actors prior to 1925, in the period where there was no statutory protection at all for performances: the early British film industry, in the 1910s, in a bid to prevent actors becoming too powerful, sought to allocate pseudonyms to actors, which would remain with the film production company after an actor's employment was terminated. This practice ended because it was illegal at common law: it was deceit for a film company to reallocate the name to a new actor, and restraint of trade for a film company to impose contractual clauses preventing the actor from using that pseudonym after termination of the employment contract.⁶⁴ As regards the right of an actor to a stage-name, it was the common law, then, that empowered actors against film companies, and not statute. Particularly in view of this history, might the courts today, through the common law, be able to provide actors with remedies in their bid to protect their performances against computer synthetisation?

The question of whether the common law tort of passing off might protect an actor's voice against its imitation was discussed in the case of *Sim v. Heinz* (1959) on an application for an interim injunction. An actor, Ron Moody had, without consent, 'simulated the voice of Alistair Sim, a well-known stage and film actor' as part of a Heinz baked-beans commercial. Supportive comments about the plaintiff's case were made at first instance: while not deciding the issue, MacNair J considered that 'it would ... be a grave defect in the law if it were possible for a party, for the purpose of commercial gain, to make use of the voice of another party without his consent.'⁶⁵ Further, while the Court of Appeal also did not decide the issue, Hodson LJ stated that he thought there may be an 'arguable case' for passing off, on the basis that the claimant's 'voice as an actor is part of his stock-in-trade and therefore is something which he is entitled to protect as part of his goods'.⁶⁶ However, amongst the 'various issues to be determined', in his view, was the question of 'whether this voice can in truth be regarded as a property'.⁶⁷

⁶³ For example, while civil rights for performers were new to legislation in 1988, the context for legislative change were a number of earlier court cases (though not all successful), as to whether the 1925 legislation, while framed as a criminal law measure, could in fact found a civil law action – particularly the right to an injunction for performers or record companies – under the common law for breach of statutory duty. See Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.p.24-32, 1-64 to 1-84.

⁶⁴ E. Cooper, 'Stock Actors, Contracts and Identity in the Film Industry in Early Twentieth Century England', discussing the business context for *Hepworth v. Ryott* [1920] 1 Ch 1, paper to be presented at the Law Culture and Humanities Annual Conference, University of Toronto, June 2023, as part of the CREATE panel, 'The Presence and Absence of Creators in Contracts, 1910-2022' also to feature papers by Amy Thomas and Kenny Barr also of CREATE, University of Glasgow.

⁶⁵ [1959] 1 WLR 313, 317.

⁶⁶ [1959] 1 WLR 313, 314 and 319.

⁶⁷ [1959] 1 WLR 313, 319.

Notwithstanding the limitations of *Sim v. Heinz* as a legal precedent, the commentary on this case in the current edition of *Performers' Rights* by Richard Arnold, writing extra-judicially, is that 'if appropriate evidence could be adduced', such a case could succeed at trial: 'an action for passing off should succeed if members of the public were led to think that, for example, a particular singer had sung a song for an advertisement contrary to the fact'.⁶⁸ Given the gaps in statutory protection for performers (noted above), could the judicial development of passing off provide sufficient protection for performers in cases of copying of a performance through digital synthetisation?

As well as possible evidential difficulties, passing off is confined to protection against misrepresentation/confusion, and will not protect against instances where the relevant public is aware that a performer is being imitated (as for example, appears to be the case in the ITVX series *Deep Fake Neighbour Wars*).⁶⁹ However, more problematically in my view, passing off requires actors to show goodwill in performing style/voice in terms of recognition amongst the relevant public; this requirement favours well-known actors with a public profile and market power, and will be a bar to protection for actors who are unknown and/or just starting their careers. Passing off, then, feeds into existing social inequalities in the acting profession, and leaves the least powerful actors, e.g. newcomers to the profession who, by definition, have no goodwill, with no remedy at all.⁷⁰ The common law, then, does not provide performers with protection sufficient to fill the gap in protection (the narrow scope) of statutory performers' rights.

The Law in Practice – Supporting Performers in the Real World

So far, my focus has been on the formal law: the current legislative rules on performers' rights contained in Part II of the Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988, as well as the common law action for passing off. However, one point that is immediately apparent on both reading Equity's *Stop AI Stealing the Show* and listening to the recent *AI/ML Media Advocacy Summit* UK Panel discussion, is that we *also* should pay serious attention to the law in practice: what happens to legal rights in the real world, particularly the relation of statutory performers' rights to

⁶⁸ Arnold, *Performers' Rights*, p.317, 10–50.

⁶⁹ S. Heritage, 'Behind the scenes of TV's first deep fake comedy: 'None of it is illegal. Everything is silly.'" *The Guardian*, 9 January 2023. On the requirement of misrepresentation in passing off see Bently and Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law*, Chapter 33.

⁷⁰ On the requirement of goodwill in passing off see Bently and Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law*, Chapter 32. The classic statement of goodwill, adopted in passing off cases is Lord Macnaghten's dicta in *IRC v. Muller's Margarine* [1901] AC 217, 224: goodwill is 'the attractive force that brings in custom'.

contractual practices. Again, I argue that an historical perspective can sharpen the critical lens on the present.

As I mentioned above, the history of copyright is intertwined with technological change and that goes right back to the advent of the printing press. Consequently, on one level, there is something very familiar about the claim in Equity's *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, that the law is out of sync with new technology; there have, indeed, been numerous instances in the past when the legislature has received petitions because the law lagged behind technology. I have already given one example of the legislature granting new rights in response, at least in part, to new technology: the campaign by painters for copyright, in view of the new threat posed by photography, culminating in the passage of the Fine Arts Copyright Act 1862.⁷¹

However, this historical comparison *also* reveals what is different about Equity's campaign today: the existing state of contracts, at the point at which the threat posed by new technology became apparent. Painters in the mid-nineteenth century (not just Royal Academicians of repute, but also oil and watercolourists more generally) were, *despite* their lack of legal rights, doing exceptionally well through contracts. Art historians today refer to the nineteenth century as the 'golden age' of the living painter, and their financial prosperity stemmed primarily from payments received for reproduction 'rights', though these did not in fact exist as a matter of law.⁷² Indeed, contracts concluded by painters and printsellers (for the sale of engraved prints of reproductions of paintings) treated painters *as if* they were first-owners of copyright and that *commercial* assumption is clear from contractual clauses granting painters generous payments and creative control (through the right to correct and approve proofs of engravings prior to publication).⁷³ Accordingly, when the legislature introduced new rights in 1862, these were, as Lionel Bently has argued, on one level an 'attempt to formalise' the existing contractual practices: 'to turn expectations into rights, powers into assignable properties, and thereby to remove the uncertainties which artists, engravers and print-sellers faced.'⁷⁴

This historical example serves to highlight the weaker contractual position that, it is claimed, actors find themselves in today. Equity's *Stop AI Stealing the Show* reports that, in the emerging AI field, it is *not* a given in contracts that the performer should be the first owner of anticipated legal rights. Indeed, Equity claims its members are poorly served by contract: a survey of its

⁷¹ See further, Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, Chapter 2.

⁷² On the 'golden age' of the living painter see G. Reitlinger, *The Economics of Taste* (London: Barrie and Rockliff, 1961), Chapter 6 and P. Gillett, *The Victorian Painter's World* (Gloucester: Alan Sutton, 1990), p.245 n.33 discussed in Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.15.

⁷³ Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, p.22, p.p.115-116 and p.p.221-222.

⁷⁴ Bently, 'Art and the Making of Modern Copyright Law', in *Dear Images* (London: Ridinghouse RCA, 2002), p.p.331-351, p.339.

members experience of new AI technology (conducted by Equity in 2021/2022 and producing 430 responses) revealed that contracts are routinely used to keep actors engaging in AI work either completely in the dark (e.g. through excessive use of non-disclosure agreements or misleading information about the purpose of recording). Further, contracts often provide for low one-off payments for the recording, accompanied by a 'rights grab' (a blanket assignment/exclusive licence of all rights subsisting in the recording) meaning there are no contractual rights to either creative control or payments for subsequent uses.⁷⁵ These weaknesses in current contractual practice, if verified by independent research, make the case for legislative reform – to provide more meaningful legal protection for *all* performers (regardless of market power⁷⁶) – yet more urgent.

Indeed, and important to note in a journal read by IP legal practitioners, the lack of commercial leverage and inequitable contractual practices, appear also to be compounded by lack of legal advice: Equity claims that in its survey, over 79% of its members who have undertaken AI work 'did not have a full understanding of their performers' rights' before signing a contract.⁷⁷ As well as legislative reform, then, serious thought needs to be given as to how actors, undertaking low-value contract work, can be better advised, whether through a pro-bono service or paid-for advice at affordable cost. As regards intellectual property litigation, the 'unmet need for justice' in low value intellectual property claims noted by the *Jackson Review* in 2009, resulted in the establishment in 2012 of the Intellectual Property Enterprise Court Small Claims Track (for cases worth under £10,000), and was part of the context for the launch of IP Pro Bono – the free legal advice service for IP disputes (established in 2016 following the call of Judge Hacon, the then IPEC presiding judge, but now 'temporarily closed').⁷⁸ However, these initiatives were all related to IP court claims, rather than non-contentious matters e.g. advice on contracts. While pro bono 'legal advice clinics' are currently offered by both CIPA and ITMA, these are restricted to advice on patents and trade marks respectively.⁷⁹ The legal advice needs of performers concluding low-value contracts, it appears, have fallen through the cracks of these initiatives.

⁷⁵ Equity, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, April 2022, 'Survey Findings' p.p.4-7.

⁷⁶ As discussed above (text to n.70), at present, any protection for performance at common law favours actors with market power.

⁷⁷ Equity, *Stop AI Stealing the Show*, April 2022, 'Survey Findings' p.4.

⁷⁸ Jackson L.J., *Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Final Report*, Dec. 2009, p.248; <https://www.ipprobono.org.uk>.

⁷⁹ <https://www.ipprobono.org.uk>.

Conclusion

Today we are used to a codified concept of 'copyright', itself a product of the legislative approach since 1911: copyright, in general, protects all subject matter on the same legal basis, regardless of the medium of expression. Yet, that approach has not always been the case: in the nineteenth century, the more frequently asked legal question was in what ways the law treated different subject matter differently (e.g. copyright rules relating to literature differed to those applying to painting).⁸⁰ In the current moment, as regards performers, we should take inspiration from this historical mindset. In its recent White Paper, *A Pro-Innovation Approach to AI Regulation*, the UK Government states that it seeks 'balance' between rights-holders, the creative industries and AI developers.⁸¹ Asking how the law regulates performers *differently* from authors, takes us to the crux of the *lack* of balance in current debates; UK Government policy documents to date have focussed on rights *in* AI content (copyright protection for computer generated works, and patent protection for AI-devised inventions) as well as licensing or exceptions to copyright *for* AI processes (specifically for text and data mining), but have not addressed existing legal differences *between* rightsholders.⁸² This point of legal difference, between authors and performers, was also notably absent in the debate '*Artificial Intelligence and the Arts: How is AI impacting the Creative Industries?*' before the House of Commons Science, Innovation and Technology Committee, on 10 May 2023, as part of the *Governance of Artificial Intelligence Inquiry* (and which post-dates the acceptance of this article by the *E.I.P.R.*).⁸³ Yet, it is that *different* treatment – the narrower scope of protection – that, at the present moment, leaves performers less well placed to deal with the challenge of AI than copyright authors, though performers and authors are affected by AI in similar ways. The pressing question now, is how that difference can be justified today.

⁸⁰ See Cooper, *Art and Modern Copyright*, Chapter 7.

⁸¹ *A Pro-Innovation Approach to AI Regulation*, March 2023, Presented to Parliament by the Secretary of State for Science, Innovation and Technology, Command Paper 815, para.35, section 3.1, 'Aims of the Regulatory Framework', which are to 'keep the right balance between protecting rights holders and our thriving creative industries, while supporting AI developers'

⁸² UK Intellectual Property Office, Consultation: Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property: Copyright and Patents, which ran from 29 October 2021 to 7 January 2022, and Consultation Outcome: Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property: Copyright and Patents: Government Response to Consultation, 28 June 2022, para.16 'About the Consultation'. *A Pro-Innovation Approach to AI Regulation*, March 2023, Presented to Parliament by the Secretary of State for Science, Innovation and Technology, Command Paper 815, para.35, section 3.1, 'Aims of the Regulatory Framework', referring to Pro-Innovation Regulation of Technologies Review: Digital Technologies, Report, presented by Sir Patrick Vallance, the Government Chief Scientific Adviser to the Chancellor of the Exchequer and to HM Government as part of the Pro-Innovation Regulation of Technologies Review, March 2023, p.8-9.

⁸³ 'Oral Evidence: Governance of Artificial Intelligence', House of Commons Science, Innovation and Technology Committee, 10 May 2023, HC 945, at Q.327-Q.411, hearing evidence from Jamie Njoku-Goodwin (UK Music), Paul Fleming (Equity), Coran Darling (DLA Piper) and Hayleigh Boshier (Brunel University).

CREATE

UK Copyright and Creative Economy Centre

School of Law / University of Glasgow

10 The Square

Glasgow G12 8QQ

www.create.ac.uk

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